

CELLULOSE ION-EXCHANGE RESINS FOR PURIFICATION AND FRACTIONATION OF PROTEINS. PART III. FRACTIONATION OF CHICK HEMOGLOBIN ON CARBOXYMETHYL CELLULOSE

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(CM)-cellulose, a cation exchanger has been successfully prepared from the indigenous sulphite pulp, and has been completely characterised. Chick hemoglobin has been resolved into two fractions by column chromatography with this cation exchanger. Rechromatography as well as electrophoresis of these two fractions confirms the existence of these two distinct fractions in chick hemoglobin.

Although chromatography has been accepted as an important laboratory technique, its application to the separation of proteins seems not to have met with general success due to the inherent complexity of the protein molecule. Considerable progress has recently been made, however, in the field of ion-exchange chromatography, and some basic proteins (Talan and Stein, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1953, 200, 507) of low molecular weight have been fractionated on Amberlite IRC-50. The chromatography of hemoglobin, a neutral protein of typical size, has been attempted by many workers on the same resin. Huisman *et al.* (*Arch. Biochem. Biophys.*, 1957, 72, 331) have reported the presence of two different hemoglobin fractions in sheep foetal hemoglobin by resolving the same on Amberlite IRC-50 column. Very recently separation of four kinds of human carbon monoxide hemoglobin with IRC-50 has been reported by Prins and Huisman (*Nature*, 1955, 175, 903). Boardman and Patridge (*Biochem. J.*, 1955, 59, 543) were also able to separate sheep foetal and carboxyhemoglobin on the same resin. But none of these methods, however, could be generally utilised as a chromatographic technique for the separation of neutral proteins due to configurational changes in protein molecule that might take place while using synthetic resins in column chromatography. Recent advances in the preparation and uses of cellulose-ion exchangers in the fractionation of proteins (Peterson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 756) and hormones (Guilleman *et al.*, *Biochem. Biophys. Acta*, 1959, 31, 252) suggested their possible use in the fractionation of hemoglobin and other proteins, virus, etc. Saha (*ibid.*, 1959, 32, 258) was able to resolve successfully chick and *Mayna* hemoglobin on (CM)-cellulose. But he did not attempt to develop a chromatographic technique on a preparative scale with (CM)-cellulose. We have, however, been able to prepare (CM)-cellulose from indigenous sulphite pulp and to develop a suitable chromatographic technique using our (CM)-cellulose as cation exchanger for the fractionation of hemoglobin; the process can be later on extended to other proteins.

In the present communication fractionation of chick hemoglobin into two components on (CM)-cellulose, substantiated by rechromatography and paper electrophoresis, has been presented.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chick hemoglobin was prepared from the whole blood of an adult chick by following the method of Huisman *et al.* (*loc. cit.*). The hemoglobin was dialysed against distilled water for 72 hours, the water having been changed several times during the process. The dialysed sample was lyophilised in cold room (4°). Hemoglobin powder of brown colour was obtained and utilised in the subsequent experiments.

Preparation of (CM)-cellulose.—Indigenous sulphite pulp was chosen as the source of cellulosic raw material. The preliminary analysis of the pulp (Table I) shows that it contains about 79% of the α -cellulose which is too small to be utilised for the preparation of resin. To obtain pure α -cellulose the pulp was given a pretreatment with 1% NaOH solution and the purified pulp was treated with 17.8% NaOH at 20° by the standard method. (CM)-cellulose was then prepared from the α -cellulose, thus obtained, by the method of Sober and Peterson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 751). The ion-exchange capacity of the resin was determined by the direct acid wash method of Eyler *et al.* (*Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1947, 19, 24). The resins having the ion-exchange capacities ranging between 0.2 and 0.3 m.e/g. were found to be suitable for our purpose as those with higher ion-exchange capacities showed a tendency to gel.

Column Chromatography.—A column of suitable dimension was prepared by the wet method according to the technique of Moore and Stein (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1948, 176, 337). Pure (CM)-cellulose resin (5 g.) was moistened with a little absolute ethanol and then suspended in 0.005 *M* sodium phosphate buffer (100 c.c.) of pH 6.8. This was the lowest concentration of the buffers employed during the subsequent elution procedure. The equilibration was carried out by allowing the slurry to settle for sometime and the supernatant liquid was replaced by a fresh quantity of buffer. This process was repeated till the pH of the supernatant fell to within 1 or 2 units of the pH of the buffer. The resin was then suspended in twice its volume, and the resulting slurry was poured in the chromatographic tube in small portions. Each portion was allowed to settle under gravity. Towards the end a uniform pressure was applied with the help of a glass rod flattened at the end. The chromatographic tube used had an internal diameter of 1.0 cm and the length of the column prepared was 20 cm. The resin in the column was supported by putting some glass wool at the bottom of the column.

A separating funnel containing developing buffer was connected to the chromatographic tube and the buffer was passed through the resin column at a flow rate of 60 c.c./hr. for 24 hrs. until the pH of the effluent was identical with that of the inflowing buffer. For the separation of the hemoglobins it was found useful to carry out the equilibration at the cold room (4°).

Having been satisfied that a good separation of an artificial mixture of albumin (coloured blue by bromophenol blue) and hemoglobin had been attained on an identical column, the fractionation of chick hemoglobin was attempted. After the excess buffer accumulated during equilibration had drained into the column, a 1.7% solution of pure chick hemoglobin in sodium phosphate buffer of 0.005 *M* and of pH 6.8 was added by a micropipette. The protein solution was allowed to drain into the resin, and walls of the tube were washed with a little developing buffer. A deep red zone was formed at the top of the column. Gradient elution was then carried out with sodium phosphate buffer of 0.005 *M*, 0.01 *M*, 0.05 *M*, 0.1 *M*, and 0.2 *M* concentrations at pH 6.8, and the effluents were collected with the help of an automatic fraction collector at every 5 minutes. The rate of flow of the buffer was 1 c.c./min. On elution a distinct red band was found to move down the column while rest of the material remained at the top of the column. After the first band had been completely eluted away, the elution was continued with the same buffer till several tubes containing colorless effluents were collected. Elution was then carried out with the buffer of higher concentrations, but no other band was found to move down the column till the concentration of the buffer was raised to 0.1 *M*, when a reddish band was found to move down the column. A small quantity of the material still remained distributed over a few cm down the column. This could not, however, be eluted away even by employing the buffer of 0.2 *M* concentration.

Spectrophotometric Measurement of the Effluent.—The optical densities of the effluents were measured at 280 m μ in a Beckman spectrophotometer (D U model). It is apparent from the

spectrophotometric curve (Fig. 1) that two relatively major peaks (A & C) appear quite apart from each other, and this suggests that the chick hemoglobin has been fractionated into two components.

Rechromatography.—The two major fractions (having high values of O. D.) corresponding to buffer of 0.005M and 0.1M were dialysed against distilled water, and concentrated sufficiently by lyophilisation in cold room. The two fractions were then subjected to rechromatography separately on the same resin, and the same technique of elution was followed as was done in the case of pure hemoglobin. Each fraction during its passage through the column was found to move as a single band down the column and showed no further resolution. This phenomenon supports the view that fractions obtained after passage through the column were not due to any defects in the column but were distinct components. (Rechromatography of peak B was omitted as the optical density was much lower compared to the other two peaks and the colour of the solution

was very faintly reddish. Nevertheless, an attempt was made to lyophilise the solution [peak B], but no solid powder could be obtained. Hence this has been ignored.)

Electrophoretic Studies of Pure Chick Hemoglobin and the Chromatographic Fractions.—Pure chick hemoglobin and its chromatographic fractions were subjected separately to paper electrophoresis.

A concentrated solution of each sample in veronal buffer (pH 8.6, ionic strength 0.05) was made and paper electrophoretic run of each solution was given in a LKB type apparatus by following the standard method (McDonald, "Ionography", p. 34, Year Book, Chicago, 1959). Since hemoglobin is a coloured protein, it could be scanned directly. The dried paper electrophorograms containing hemoglobin spots were evaluated by direct scanning with the help of a photovolt densitometer (Transmission type, Model 525). The curves were then drawn by plotting the densities against migration distance in mm. While the electrophoretic pattern of pure chick hemoglobin showed two peaks, the electrophoretic pattern of the individual chromatographic fraction showed single peak in each case (Fig. 2).

- (a) Pure hemoglobin.
 (b) Chromatographic fraction A.
 (c) Chromatographic fraction C.
 Buffer: veronal.
 Ionic strength: 0.05.
 pH: 8.6
 Potential difference: 220 volts.
 Time: 16 hours.

TABLE I

Analysis of the sulphite pulp.
 (Mean of three sets of values).

Moisture content	.. 3.22%	β -Cellulose	.. 11.69%
Ash content	.. 3.56	γ -Cellulose	.. 5.65
α -Cellulose	.. 78.69	Ethanol-benzene extractable	.. 0.27

DISCUSSION

During the elution it was observed that a portion of the hemoglobin remained distributed down the column. This material could not be eluted away even by use of the strongest buffer (0.2M sodium phosphate). This can be attributed to the phenomenon of tailing or to presence of a third component, which could not be identified. But this was in no way connected with the denaturation of proteins as the whole experiment was conducted in a cold room (4°). The two fractions obtained after passage of chick hemoglobin through (CM)-cellulose column as well as rechromatography of the individual fractions provide sufficient evidence that the chick hemoglobin consists of two components. This has been further confirmed by the spectrophotometric and

electrophoretic studies. Thus, it is observed that (CM)-cellulose has proved to be an excellent and cheap adsorbent for the fractionation of chick hemoglobin.

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